

**EFFECTIVENESS OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING
JUMPING ABILITY IN YOUNG GYMNASTS**

Yusupov Toyirjon Tulanovich

Senior Lecturer at the Department of Types of Sports Activities,

Fergana State University

Abstract This article presents the results of a pedagogical experiment aimed at improving the motor potential of young gymnasts at the initial stage of their sports development. The results of physical status testing are provided, as well as data from a year-long experiment evaluating the improvement of the motor quality of jumping ability in young gymnasts.

Keywords: Pedagogical experiment, heterochronism, jumping ability, innovative methodology, motor qualities.

The nature of the motor potential manifestation in gymnastics exercises is that it is a complex coordination sport that requires maximum display of jumping ability, motor skills, abilities, and physical capacities. Monitoring literary sources on the issue related to the development of jumping ability and ensuring effective development of basic motor and coordination skills is a priority in the system of school physical education.

The current level of gymnastics development is unthinkable without the highest development of the special motor qualities inherent to this type of sporting activity. One of these physical qualities is jumping ability, where the ability to concentrate muscular and volitional efforts in a minimal period of time is especially evident. V.M. Zatsiorsky (3), in his book *"The Physical Qualities of an Athlete"*, describes jumping ability as one of the important aspects of motor activity and points out that achieving high sports results in gymnastics is impossible without a proper level of development of jumping ability.

To develop jumping ability, a pedagogical experiment was conducted involving 24 young gymnasts aged 12-14 years. Based on preliminary pedagogical testing of physical development and motor abilities, two groups of 12 boys each were formed, having the same level of jumping ability, evaluated by the test "standing long jump" and V.M. Abalakova's methodology.

The level of physical development of the young gymnasts was determined, and the anthropometric characteristics included in the battery were: height and body mass, chest circumference, vital lung capacity, and dynamometric indicators.

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According to the results of the pedagogical testing, at the prepubertal age period of 12 years, the height of the boys was 143 ± 5.0 cm, while 13-year-olds exceeded 12-year-olds by 5 cm (6.64%), ($t=7.14$), with an average height of 148 ± 6.0 cm. (Table 1)

Evaluating body mass indicators, the boys at the age of 12 years had an average weight of 36.4 ± 4.5 kg, while the 13-year-olds exceeded them by 2.7 kg (6.91%), ($t=3.48$). It should be noted that over the two-year period, the difference in body weight indicators was 6.3 kg (14.76%), which is confirmed by the opinions of many authors who conducted research on a similar age group of boys.

Table: Physical Development Indicators of Young Gymnasts

Indicators	12 y. n=12		13 y. n=12		Difference %	t
	X	σ	X	σ		
Height, cm	143	5.0	148	6.0	6,64	7,1
Body Mass, kg	36.4	4.5	39.1	3.5	6,91	3,4
Chest Circumference (OGK), cm	70.8	5.7	73.7	4.2	5,94	2,4
Vital Lung Capacity (VLC), ml	1800	30	1900	30	5,27	2,0
Dynamometry, kg	22.5	4.4	25.3	4.5	8,07	2,3
Deadlift Strength, kg	37.2	4.2	39.4	3.7	5,59	2,2

An analogous picture was observed when assessing respiratory indicators, where it was found that the **chest circumference (OGK)** at the age of 12 years was 70.8 ± 5.7 cm, and at 13 years old, this indicator was 73.7 ± 4.2 cm, with an increase of 2.9 cm (5.94%) ($t=2.41$).

The **vital lung capacity** at the age of 12 was 1800 ± 30 ml, while at 13 years of age, this indicator was slightly higher by 5.27% ($t=2.41$). However, no significant

differences were found in this physiological test, and the values remain within the normal physiological range.

According to dynamometric characteristics, it was found that at the age of 12, the value was 22.5 ± 4.4 kg, while at 13 years, there was a significant increase of 11.07% ($t=2.33$). **Deadlift strength**, which is a critical factor in gymnastics, at 12 years of age was 37.2 ± 4.2 kg, and at 13 years, there was a significant increase of 2.2 kg (5.59%). It should be noted that the anthropometric measurements for all studied parameters are at a satisfactory level.

The conducted **pedagogical testing of motor abilities** on a group of 12-13-year-old boys specializing in gymnastics, based on physical preparation tests borrowed from state standards for physical education, revealed that the **speed abilities** of the boys in the 60m sprint at the age of 12 was 11.6 ± 0.93 sec. At 13 years, a slight improvement in results was observed, with a 0.44% increase ($t=1.22$). (Table 2)

Endurance, as an important motor quality in gymnastics, was assessed based on the 1500m run test. It was found that the boys at the age of 12 had a result of 12.1 ± 0.35 minutes, while at 13 years, they covered the 2000m distance, as stipulated in the regulatory documents, in 11.3 ± 0.86 minutes (4, 5).

Table 2: Physical Fitness Indicators of Young Gymnasts Aged 12-13

Indicators	12 y.		13 y.		Difference %	t
	n=12		n=12			
	X	σ	X	σ		
Run 60 м, с	11.6	0.93	11.5	1.30	0,44	4.2
Run 1500 м. мин.с.	12,1	0,35				
Run 2000 м.мин..с.			11,3	0,86		
Pull-ups , reps	3.2	0.48	3.6	0.64	11,1	3,0
Push-ups from a prone position , reps	5,0	1.01	6.3	1.30	20,6	6.5
Overall flexibility , cm	2.3	0.54	3,0	0.54	23,3	7.7

Standing long jump, cm	170	0.09	205	0.16	17,1	1,7
Standing long jump, cm	144	7,0	158	9,0	8,9	4.6
Tennis ball throw, m	23.6	2.5	29.4	2.9	19,7	11.6

Strength Abilities of 12-Year-Old Boys

The results of the "**pull-ups on the horizontal bar**" test showed an average of 3.2 ± 0.48 repetitions at the age of 12, with a significant progressive increase by the age of 13, reaching 3.6 ± 0.64 repetitions, marking a difference of 11.1% ($t=3.0$). In the "**push-ups from a prone position**" test, the 12-year-olds showed a result of 5.0 ± 1.01 repetitions, and at 13 years, there was an increase of 20.6%, with an average result of 6.3 ± 1.30 repetitions.

According to A.A. Gushalovsky, individual strength development rates, as an indicator of the heterochronic factor, depend on the timing of sexual maturation, which must be considered by coaches conducting the training process.

The manifestation of the **speed-strength factor** was assessed using the "**standing long jump**" test. The 12-year-olds showed a result of 170 ± 9.0 cm, and by the age of 13, there was a significant increase in the result ($t=4.6$) by 17.1%, reaching an average of 205 ± 16.0 cm. Similar changes were observed in the **standing long jump from a standing position** test.

The widely used **tennis ball throw test**, which measures speed-strength qualities, is included in all program-normative documents. The 12-year-old gymnasts showed a result of 23.6 ± 2.5 meters, while the 13-year-olds significantly outperformed them by 19.7% ($t=11.6$), with a result of 29.4 ± 2.9 meters.

Analyzing the results of the pedagogical testing of the motor readiness level of the young gymnasts, it was found that their physical abilities were at a satisfactory level, providing a basis for introducing significant corrections into the training process to improve the preparation system of young gymnasts.

Considering the physical status indicators of the young gymnasts during the pedagogical experiment, all training sessions in the experimental groups were conducted 3 times a week, lasting 1.5 hours each, and were of a comprehensive nature. To achieve the set objectives, an innovative methodology was developed, consisting of specially selected complexes of physical exercises, focusing on the predominant development of jumping ability.

During the pedagogical experiment, jumping ability development was systematically carried out at the end of the main part of the training, with the core of the developed training complexes consisting of exercises aimed at developing the calf muscles, muscles of the front and rear thigh surfaces, and strengthening the ankle muscles.

Depending on the type of physical exercise complexes used, various methods of organizing sessions were employed (front-facing, group, flow, individual, and game-based). The number of repetitions of exercises progressively increased with each training session as the young gymnasts adapted to the proposed training loads.

The conducted pedagogical experiment showed that the young gymnasts outperformed their peers in the control group on all the studied indicators. (Table 3)

Table 3: Results of the Pedagogical Experiment

Periods	Groups	Standing long jump, cm.	P	Test by S.M. Abalakov	P
Before the experiment	Control group	131,8±1,88	>0,05	19,7±0,59	>0,05
	Experimental group	131,2±1,92		19,9±0,58	
After the experiment	Control group	138,3±1,81	<0,05	22,4±0,60	<0,05

	Experimental group	143,6±1,65		24,4±0,63	
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The **experimental program** integrated into the training process, along with its methodology using specially developed complexes of physical exercises aimed at improving the motor quality of jumping ability, has demonstrated high effectiveness and is recommended for use in the training process of young gymnasts at the initial stage of their sports development.

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